

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF SMART STRUCTURES WITH OVERWRAP COMPOSITES BY USING FIBRE OPTIC SENSORS

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SUMMARY: The structural health monitoring in-service is very important and definitely demanded for safely working of engineering structure such as composite structures, concrete structures. It is very difficult to carry out by using conventional methods. Embedded fibre optic sensors can offer new method to detect structural damage during the service period. In this paper, the compression tests of smart concrete structures with wrapping CFRP composite materials embedded EFPI and FBG sensors have been performed. The results indicate that the dynamic and static measurement capability of fibre optic sensor is proved. The results also show that the compressive strain on the surface of concrete cylinder is much higher than that on the surface of wrapped composite materials. Thus, the embedded fibre optic sensors can be used to monitor the change of strain condition and failure of concrete materials earlier and more sensitively.

KEYWORDS: Structural health monitoring (SHM), Fibre optic sensor, EFPI, FBG, Smart structures, Composite materials

1. INTRODUCTION

The structural health monitoring in-service is very important and definitely demanded for safely working of engineering structure such as concrete structures. It is very difficult to carry out by using conventional methods. New reinforced concrete construction would benefit greatly from in situ structural monitors that could detect a decrease in performance or imminent failure, for example, variation in strain, temperature, corrosion, or crack formation. The ability to interrogate numerous sensors multiplexed along a single fibre permits an entire structure to be outfitted with sensors with a manageable number of leads routed to central access points. In response to the increased need, various techniques are being developed and some of the most promising are based on the use of fibre optic sensors (FOS). [1-3]

Fibre optic smart structures are an enabling technology that will allow engineer to add a nervous system to their designs, enabling damage assessment, vibration damping, and many other capabilities to structures that would be very difficult to achieve by other means. The potential market for the application of smart civil structures can be quite large. The most probable candidates will be smart civil structures such as smart building and skyscrapers, smart bridge, dams, bridge decks etc. Fibre optic sensors (FOS) can offer many potential

advantages for application to civil structural systems. In fact, a lot of fibre optic sensors have been developed for use in smart civil structure such as polarisation FOS, Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometric (EFPI), and fibre Bragg grating (FBG), multimode FOS, etc.. These fibre optic sensors already have been used to monitor the structural health status of composite and concrete structures successfully.[4-7]

In this paper, the compression tests of smart concrete structures with wrapping CFRP composite materials embedded EFPI and FBG sensors have been performed. The results indicate that the dynamic and static measurement capability of fibre optic sensor is proved.

2. EXTRINSIC FABRY-PEROT INTERFEROMETRIC (EFPI) and FIBER BRAGG GRATING (FBG) SENSORS

2.1 Extrinsic Fabry-Perot interferometric (EFPI) sensor

The basic principle of EFPI sensor is based on the multi-reflection Fabry-Perot interference between the two reflected mirrors. The schematic configuration of Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometric sensor is shown in Figure 1. The EFPI sensor is made using a two single mode optical fibre as the two reflectors. The two fibres are inserted and fused into a quartz capillary tube with a larger diameter.

The two-components epoxy also been used to strengthening the bond between the bare fibres and capillary. In this EFPI sensor, a cavity comprising two reflectors that are parallel to each other and perpendicular to the axis of the optical fibres. The cavity length between the two surfaces of optical fibres is changed when an external load is applied onto this sensor. This can be measured by a CCD spectrometer through a 3dB 2x2 fibre coupler. The strain of the sensor is given according the following equation [4]:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta d}{L} \quad (1)$$

Where Δd is the change of the cavity length, L is the gauge length that is the distance between the two fusion spliced points on the micro capillary.

Fig. 1: Schematic configuration of Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometric (EFPI) sensor

2.2 Fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensor

As far as we know the uniform fibre Bragg grating (FBG) includes a segment of optical fibre in which a periodic modulation of the core refractive index as shown in Figure 2. Usually, in-fibre FBG can be fabricated on the photosensitive (Ge-doped or hydrogen soaked) single mode optical fibre by using the UV laser source in wavelength 240-248nm. Basically, the principle of the FBG sensor is based on the measurement of the changes in reflective signal,

which is the centre wavelength of back-reflected light from a Bragg grating, depends on the effective refractive index of the core and the periodicity of the grating. According the Bragg condition, the Bragg wavelength can be expressed as [8] :

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{eff}\Lambda \quad (2)$$

Where λ_B is Bragg grating wavelength, Λ is grating periodic spacing, n_{eff} is the effective reflective index of the fibre core. So the Bragg wavelength will shift with changes in either n_{eff} or Λ . When an external mechanical or thermal deformation is imposed onto the grating area, the effective reflective index will change as well as the periodic spacing.

Fig. 2: Schematic illustration of Fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensor

3. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND DISCUSSIONS

The schematic illustration of CFRP wrapped concrete cylinder with FOSs and strain gauges was shown in Figure 3. The concrete cylinder was fabricated with a water/cement ratio of 0.52, an aggregate/cement ratio of 6. The dimension of concrete cylinder is 200mm (length) x 100mm (diameter). Two layers CFRP composite prepreps from Sika Ltd. were then wrapped on the surface of concrete cylinder using special designed adhesive Sika-30 as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Schematic illustration of CFRP wrapped concrete cylinder with FOSs and strain gauges

A FBG sensor was surface mounted on the surface of concrete cylinder in longitudinal direction. An EFPI sensor was embedded in the CFRP composite prepreps in same direction

to evaluate the strain transfer before laid up it directly on the concrete surface. For the strain measurement in hoop direction, a FBG sensor was also embedded in the CFRP composite prepregs. A biaxial electrical resistance strain (ERS) gauge (PLC-60-11 from TML) was externally bonded on the outside composite surface of wrapped concrete cylinder at the same location that sensors were embedded as the reference measurement. High flexible thin PTFE tubes with 0.4mm in diameter were used to protect the fibre at entrance location to reduce the risk of fibre breakage that may caused by the sharp bending or other unexpected damage. The EFPI and FBG sensors were interrogated using Ocean Optics CCD spectrometers through a 3dB optical coupler separately. The compression failure test of wrapped concrete cylinder was carried out in the ETS structural testing system. All sensor data are automatically captured by programmed Labview software through a data acquisition card from National Instrument.

The experimental results of CFRP wrapped concrete cylinder with embedded EFPI and FBG sensors were shown in Figure 4. Obviously, It is can be seen that the measured strain using EFPI and FBG sensors in both longitudinal and hoop directions have excellent agreement compared with results obtained from electrical resistance strain (ERS) gauges. It is note that the measured strain in longitudinal direction is compressive strain, whereas the strain is tensile strain in hoop direction. It is emerged that the ultimate failure strain in longitudinal direction is about $4600 \mu\epsilon$, which is much higher than that in hoop direction when the compressive stress applied to 56 MPa. For the hoop tensile strain, the strain measured from FBG sensor and ERS gauge provide a linear stress strain relationship below 43 MPa. After that point, the measured strain in hoop direction was slightly diverged. It is noted that the strain rate inside of CFRP prepregs in the longitudinal direction is between that on the surface of concrete cylinder and surface of CFRP materials after 42 MPa. It is speculated the different strain transfer effectivity from insider concrete to outer composite materials.

Apparently, it is also found that the longitudinal strain obtained by FBG sensor is always higher than that measured by EFPI sensor inside of CFRP materials and strain gauge on the surface of composite materials. Thus, the FBG sensor can monitor the strain condition and failure of the concrete materials can be monitored and detected by using FBG earlier than the conventional ERS gauge, which is mounted on the surface of the outer reinforcement materials. Both embedded EFPI and FBG sensors were working properly during the failure test until the concrete cylinder collapsed. The photographs of CFRP wrapped concrete cylinder with embedded EFPI and FBG sensors were shown in Figure 5. The experiments of dynamic strain measurement also have been performed using FBG sensor as shown in Figure 6. It proves the dynamic monitoring capability of FBG sensor for smart structures.

Fig. 4: Ultimate compression curves of concrete cylinder with wrapped CFRP prepregs using FBG and EFPI sensors

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Photographs of CFRP wrapped concrete cylinder with embedded EFPI and FBG sensors (a) Before the ultimate failure test (b) After ultimate failure test

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: Dynamic strain measurement of concrete cylinder with wrapped CFRP prepregs using FBG sensor (a) Vertical direction (b) Hoop direction

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the CFRP wrapped concrete cylinder was investigated by using FBG, EFPI sensors and electrical resistance strain (ERS) gauges. Some important conclusions can be obtained:

- a. The fibre optic sensors (FOSs) can be used to mentoring the strain development of concrete structures.
- b. The results of compression tests of concrete cylinder with CFRP protected fibre optic sensors exhibit very good linear sensor properties and excellent agreement compared with electrical resistance strain gauges.
- c. The results for wrapped CFRP composites also show that the compressive strain on the surface of concrete cylinder is much higher then that on the surface of wrapped composite materials. Thus, the embedded fibre optic sensors can be used to monitor the change of strain condition and failure of concrete materials earlier and more sensitively.

Therefore, the fibre optic sensors can be used in the smart civil structures such as smart bridge, smart highway, smart building in future for different type of the FOS such as Fibre Bragg grating, fluorescence-based temperature sensors, etc..

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